

Project Title	UKRI Transforming Food Systems - Study Two: Policies for more sustainable and healthy food systems for all in the UK
Status	Draft
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Applicant Status	Staff (Lecturer in Sustainable Development)
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External Collaborators	Yes
Funder/Project Title	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council - Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvant
Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council

Ethical Review Application ER/KP763/3 (continued)

Project Description

'Policies for more sustainable and healthy food systems for all in the UK' is a research study that is part of the broader £6M UKRI-funded research programme 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'.

This study is particularly focusing on mapping as well as assessing the different policies that shape UK's current agrifood systems, as well as identifying policy gaps, change and pathways that would lead to more sustainable and healthy food systems for all, especially those communities who are experiencing food inequalities. The study will involve different research activities, including semi-structured interviews, focus groups and workshops, through which the UK's policy landscape and different policy options for sustainable, healthy and just food systems will be identified and assessed. Research activities will involve representatives of key stakeholder groups and organisations with an interest in UK's agro-food system (e.g. policy experts, policy officials and policy advocacy groups, key industry stakeholders from farming and retail sectors, community food organisations, etc).

This research study is part of the bigger UKRI-funded project. Dr Katerina Psarikidou and Dr Elaine Swan are the project research investigators based at the University of Sussex. Based on the principles of research co-production, the project is envisioned to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse communities with choice and agency over the food they consume, the chains through which they access their food, and the policy frameworks that are needed to support the vision of a more inclusive and socio-environmentally just agri-food system for all.

This particular study is aimed to shed light on the policy frameworks that shape the UK's current agrifood policy landscape, assess these policies, identify policy gaps as well as possibilities and proposals for policy transformation and change. The study will also focus on the impact of such policies on those communities that may be experiencing food inequalities, and the types of policies that would enable more equitable access to sustainable and healthy food. Speaking to key stakeholder groups representing diverse communities of actors is a key research element that would help gather significant evidence on the types of policies (or lack of them) in configuring more sustainable and healthy food systems for all.

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/KP763/3)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	No
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	No
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	No
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	No
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	
A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.	

Ethical Review Form Section B (ER/KP763/3)

Question	Response
>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)	
B1. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?	<p>Interviews will be conducted with 15-20 individuals, representatives of different stakeholder groups with an interest in sustainable agrifood systems. These will include policy experts, policy officials and policy advocacy groups, key industry stakeholders from farming and retail sectors, community food organisations. Initial interviews will be conducted with our non-academic project partners and advisory board members from the public, private and third sectors. These will also help with snowballing and identification of additional interest groups to be approached and interviewed.</p> <p>Follow-up stakeholder workshops will involve an approximate number of 10 individuals per workshop. It will be an approximate of 2 workshops. This will involve a combination of our interviewees and other policy experts.</p>
B2. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?	<p>Research participants will be initially contacted via email, providing information about the project as well as the aims of the interview/workshops they are invited to participate, including in the form of participant information sheets.</p> <p>Initial interviews will take place with some of the project's non-academic partners and advisory board members. This is a key method of also keeping research partners and their input centre stage in the project. It will also help with identifying and recruiting additional research participants. Desk-web research on policies will also help with identifying key stakeholder groups involved in debates.</p> <p>The workshops will be based on a combination of our interviewees and new research participants particularly from the policy world. With regards to the recruitment of interviewees for workshops, consent forms are asking interviewees to express interest in follow-up research activities. Identification of new research participants will be based on desk/web research and snowballing. Recruitment will take place via email.</p>

B3. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording?	One-to-one interviews and Multi-stakeholder workshops will be the two key research methods. Interviews will help with the mapping of the policy landscape and sharing of experiences from each stakeholder group. Multi-stakeholder workshops will help broaden the discussion around policies, particularly evaluating the current policy landscape and assessing different policy options that would help configure more sustainable and healthy food systems for all, particularly those experiencing food inequalities. Both methods will be supported by audio or audio-visual recordings. This is also clearly stated in the participant information sheet and consent forms.
B4. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?	<p>Due to diverse uncertainties around covid, interviews will take place on zoom for education supported by the University of Sussex platform. Researchers already have access to platform and are acquainted with security settings due to teaching commitments. Interviewees will be informed about that through the participant information sheets and asked to provide their consent to this.</p> <p>Depending on covid restrictions, workshops may also take place on zoom. If possible, they may be arranged in central London venues rented through the project budget, to enable participation of representatives from different bodies and parts of the country. Again, participants will be informed about that and requested to provide their consent.</p>
B5. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of potentially distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.	No. Participants are experts who will be giving their professional input on policies for sustainable, healthy, accessible and just food systems.
>> Confidentiality and Anonymity	
B6. Will questionnaires be completed anonymously and returned indirectly?	N/A
B7. Will research data only be identifiable by a unique identifier (e.g. code/pseudonym)? If Yes, please explain how this will be attributed in B11a below.	Yes
B8. Will lists of identity numbers or pseudonyms linked to names and/or addresses be stored securely and separately from the research data? If Yes, explain how this will occur in B11a below.	Yes
B9. Will all place names and institutions which could lead to the identification of individuals or organisations be changed unless this is consented to explicitly in the consent form?	Yes
B10. Will all personal information gathered be treated in strict confidence and never disclosed to any third parties?	Yes
B11. Can you confirm that your research records will be held in accordance with data protection regulations? (http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa)	Yes

<p>B11a. Please explain how ANY identifiable personal and/or research data will be managed and securely stored ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this.</p>	<p>The names of all research participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities, as will the name of the organisations they represent / work for. For the purposes of publications, if needed for narrating purposes, real names will be replaced with pseudonyms. This will also be clear to research participants in the consent forms, to which participants will be asked to consent too.</p> <p>All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using Sussex Box. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to Box, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. Participant names and names of organisations will be replaced with pseudonyms.</p> <p>Zoom audio-visual recordings will also be securely downloaded and code-protected, prohibiting access to any external users. The resulting files will be removed and deleted from zoom, and will be kept securely in the University-approved Box storage. Following university advice, participants will be clearly informed about the fact that this audio-visual material will be maintained in university storage systems. Transcripts of this material will also be produced and uploaded onto the storing system.</p> <p>The shared project workspace on Box will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to research team.</p>
<p>B12. Do you intend to use the research data for any purpose other than that for which consent is explicitly given? If so, please explain below</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B12a. If you answered NO to any of the above in this section (or think more information could be useful to the reviewer) please explain here:</p>	
<p>>> Informed Consent and Recruitment of Participants</p>	
<p>B13. Will all respondents be given an Information Sheet and be given adequate time to read it before being asked to agree to participate?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B14. Will all participants taking part in an interview, focus group, observation (or other activity which is not questionnaire based) be asked to sign a consent form? If you are obtaining consent another way (such as verbally), please explain under B17 below.</p>	<p>Yes</p>

B15. Will all participants self-completing a questionnaire be asked to show consent to participate by a specific and identifiable action? (Give details in B17 below)	Yes
B16. Will all participants be told that they can withdraw their participation at any time during the research and can ask for their data to be destroyed and/or removed from the project until it is no longer practical to do so?	Yes
B17. If you answered NO to any of the above in this section (or think more information will be useful to the reviewer) please explain here:	
>> Context	
B18. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete the next question.	No
B19. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.	No
B19a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).	
B20. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?	Yes
B20a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? If undertaken overseas you must attach an OTSSRA form. In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has specific travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment. https://www.gov.uk/foreign-travel-advice	Interviews will take place online via the University of Sussex Zoom platform. Unique codes/passwords will be provided to maintain the safety of both parties involved. Workshops will take place in central sites that are specifically tailored and designed for purposes of holding multi-stakeholder events/workshops. The selection of such sites through official routes will also maintain the appropriateness of the selected sites and the safety of both researchers and research participants. No research will take place overseas.
B21. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?	Yes
B21a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of the lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?	As described above, interviews will take place online. This, in itself, can maintain good levels of personal physical safety for all members involved. Unique passwords/codes will also help facilitate processes of safety in the online context.
>> Any further concerns	
B22. Are there any other ethical considerations relating to your project which have not been covered above?	No
B22a. If yes, please explain:	

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Policies for more sustainable and healthy food systems for all in the UK
Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, Dr Elaine Swan and UKRI Research Fellow (Business School)
C-REC Ref no:

Please tick box

YES NO

- *I consent to take part in the interview/ workshop that is being undertaken by the researcher(s).*

- *I agree to allowing the interview/ workshop to be photographed and audio-recorded/recorded, and then be made into an anonymised written transcript.*

- *I agree to allowing the interviews/workshops to be conducted and audio-recorded via the University of Sussex zoom, and be stored in the University of Sussex storing systems.*

- *I agree to being informed about follow-up research activities and participate, should I be available.*

- *I understand that any information given by me may be used in future reports, academic articles, publications or presentations by the researcher and the project team, but my personal information will not be included and I will not be identifiable.*

- *I understand that data will be kept according to the university guidelines for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the study.*

- *I understand that any information that is provided is confidential, and that no information that is disclosed will lead to the identification of any individual in future reports and publications, either by the researcher or by any other party.*

- *If I am participating in the workshop/focus group, I understand that any information disclosed within the workshop/meeting remains confidential to the group, and I will not discuss the workshop with or in front of anyone who was not involved unless I have the relevant person's permission.*

- *However, I understand that confidentiality cannot always be guaranteed for information which I might disclose in the focus groups/workshops.*
- *I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved.*
- *I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with [Data Protection legislation](#).*
- *I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.*
- *I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project.*

Name:

Signature

Date:

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET TEMPLATE

STUDY TITLE

Policies for more sustainable, healthy and just food systems for all in the UK.

INVITATION PARAGRAPH

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

This study is part of a broader UKRI-funded project entitled 'Co-producing sustainable and healthy food systems for disadvantaged communities'. This study is particularly focusing on mapping as well as assessing the different policies that shape UK's current agrifood systems, as well as identifying policy change and pathways that would lead to more sustainable and healthy food systems for all, especially those communities who are experiencing food inequalities. As part of a five-year project, the study will develop in different stages and will involve different research activities, including semi-structured interviews, focus groups and co-creation workshops, through which the UK's policy landscape and different policy options for sustainable, healthy and just food systems will be identified and assessed.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You are invited to take part in this study as an expert, representative of a key stakeholder group, policy maker or policy advocacy group, or as an academic, with a long term experience and work on sustainable agro-food systems. You will be specifically asked to provide your input on the role of different policies in shaping the UK's food system as well as the particular parts/practices of the system that your work/experience is embedded. You will also be asked to contribute to envisioning or exploring policy change and pathways that would contribute to a more sustainable, healthy and equitable food system in the UK.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You are invited to take part in a semi-structured interview or a focus group/workshop through which you will be providing your knowledge and input on mapping as well as assessing the policy landscape shaping the UK's agro-food system now and in the future. These activities will take one to two hours of your time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART? (WHERE APPROPRIATE)

There are no risks involved in participating. However, we appreciate that asking for 1 to 2 hours of your time is a commitment.

Template approved by URGC 8 May 2018

<Project Title>

Page 1 of 3

<Version Number>

<Date>

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

If you take part in this study, your insights will contribute to proposing more integrated agrifood policy frameworks that would configure more sustainable, healthy food systems that are available and accessible for all. The project will also contribute to a policy brief including a number of policy recommendations that would emanate from the feedback received from experts as well as people from the local communities. It is also envisioned to bring together key stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, to discuss about how to build more equitable food systems in the UK, and to learn from each other, and support each other towards this common goal. It is envisioned to lead to some practical recommendations, which will be informed by you and will hopefully provide some helpful insights for the organisations you work for .

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?¹

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018.

After the interview/workshop, only the researchers will have access to your input. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g. your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcript produced by the transcriber. This means that we will remove any personal information.

This research project involves the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: [Zoom Privacy Policy](#) . All audio-visual data collected will be downloaded and stored securely on a University of Sussex managed storing system, named Box.

All participants in workshops are requested to consent to keep all information disclosed within the workshops confidential, and not discuss the workshop with or in front of anyone who was not involved unless I have the relevant person's permission. However, as also noted in the consent form, it is also acknowledged that confidentiality cannot always guaranteed within group discussions.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form and making yourself available for the meeting and discussion.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform a number of academic as well as non-academic publications. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, as well as policy and best practice documents. Results will also be presented at academic and practitioner conferences. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes (e.g. from the interview/focus group with you), so that although we will use your exact words, you cannot be identified in the publications. The writing and publication process is planned to take place over a 5 year period, with data retained for the length of that period.

¹ As a researcher, **two** principles are important here. Firstly the '*Common law duty of confidentiality*' by which all participants, unless specifically informed otherwise can expect that the researcher will treat what they have received with confidentiality. Secondly, the requirements of [data protection legislation](#) that apply to all types of personal data that are processed. Failure to act in accordance with the principles and requirements of either may be considered research misconduct.

Template approved by URGC 8 May 2018

<Project Title>

<Version Number>

<Date>

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research is undertaken by the Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a larger UKRI research study entitled 'Co-producing Healthy Sustainable Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading. The Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) is leading research on policy.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been improved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is [XX/XXXX/X].

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Katerina Psarikidou from SPRU by emailing a.psarikidou@sussex.ac.uk or Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. Any concerns regarding the way in which the study has been conducted should be directed toward [X] (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project) by emailing [X]

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

THANK YOU

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Your participation in this research will be greatly appreciated.

Template approved by URGC 8 May 2018

<Project Title>

Page 3 of 3

<Version Number>

<Date>

Research Questions

1. Could you please tell us a few things about you, the organisation you work for, and its relevance to agriculture and food?
2. How do you think your organisation contributes to more sustainable and healthy food systems in the country?
3. Is there any particular work done that can (in)directly contribute to more sustainable healthy food for disadvantaged communities?
4. Do you believe that the UK's agrifood system is sustainable and healthy? In which ways? In which ways not?
5. Are there any particular challenges that disadvantaged communities currently face with regards to that?
6. How important do you think policies are in shaping the UK's food system, as it currently is?
7. Are there any particular policies that affect the work of your organisation in this area, either positively or negatively? Have you got any recommendations for policy that would help support the work of your organisation?
8. Are there any particular policies that you believe are important in shaping the (un)sustainability of the UK's food system?
9. What are there any policies or measures missing that could contribute towards more sustainable food systems in the country?
10. Are there any particular policies that you believe are important in shaping the (un)healthiness of the UK's food system?
11. Are there any particular measures or policies (potentially missing) that you believe could contribute to more healthy food systems?
12. Do you believe the current policy landscape addresses issues of equality with regards to accessing food?
13. How about policies with regards to accessing sustainable, healthy food? Is this possible?
14. What policy changes would help address issues of food poverty and inequality?
15. Can you identify any deficits in the policy making process that work against the goal of transforming food systems in more sustainable and healthy directions for all?
16. Who is involved in the making of the policies? Who is not there, but ought to be there? Why?
17. How can we design/configure policies that take into consideration the needs of the disadvantaged communities?
18. Can we assess policies against local community needs?
19. What are the different policy options that we should be considering for configuring sustainable healthy food systems for disadvantaged communities?
20. Are there any particular recommendations that would enable more inclusive processes for policy making, also within the remits of this project?
21. Who else should we be talking to as part of this project?
22. What other questions are important for you for us to ask?